

Bismuth trichloride – A clean, green catalyst for the synthesis of Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines (DHPs)

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Abstract : Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines (DHPs) are synthesized in good to excellent yields from aldehydes, 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds and ammonium acetate using bismuth trichloride which acts as mild Lewis acid promoter and 10 mol% is enough for this protocol under solvent free conditions.

Keywords : Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines, bismuth trichloride, aldehydes, 1,3-dicarbonyl compound, ammonium acetate, solvent-free.

Introduction

Originally in 1881¹ Hantzsch reported a process for the production of 1,4-DHPs which were readily oxidized to produce pyridines and it was accepted as a good process for the preparation of a variety of substituted pyridines. Later on when their resemblance to NADH² (A) was reported, these started attracting priority of chemists to use these molecules as organo-reducers and a variety of functional groups have been successfully reduced³⁻⁶. During this process DHPs are oxidized to substitute pyridines. Also several other inorganic oxidants are used to achieve this target⁷⁻¹⁰. Further intensive researches were followed after the disclosure of their interesting anti-hypertensive pharmacological activity¹¹ and a systematic approach have resulted in the discovery of drugs like Nifedipine, Aranidipine, Nicardipine, Nitrendipine and Amlodipine etc. which are drugs of choice in the market¹².

In addition, DHPs are also been shown to possess activities like antithrombotics¹³, calcium channel blockers¹⁴, anti-inflammatory¹⁵, anti-tumor¹⁶, antituberculosis¹⁷, analgesic¹⁸ and anti-convulsant agents¹⁹ etc. which puts DHP moiety in a class of privileged molecules¹². Developing an easy and efficient method for their production is on priority list of chemists, as the original procedure reported by Arthur Hantzsch was flawed in many ways¹. Choice of Lewis acid should be such that it does not trigger dearylation of DHP's. So to produce these molecules economically in high yields, additives/catalysts continue to be reported. Mechanistically this reaction is established to proceed via. Knoevengel reactions followed by Michael reaction in all eventuality two molecules of water are eliminated²⁰. In pursuit to achieve higher efficiency, several catalysts and conditions are tried, which include use of microwaves²¹, ionic liquids²², Lewis

(A)

acids like $\text{Yb}(\text{OTf})_2^{23}$, CAN^{24} , $\text{K}_7[\text{PW}_{11}\text{CoO}_{40}]^{25}$, I_2^{26} etc. are already reported. From a careful scrutiny of above processes, it was concluded that a scope of further improvement in these production processes of DHPs was still there as some of these procedures are either very slow, require long time and still some afforded not very good yields. Applications of BiCl_3 in organic synthesis are of current interest and various attractive properties because of its being a mild Lewis acid, are reported. It is safe, nontoxic and mild and does not leave any corrosive residues on aqueous work up.

Results and discussion

Our continuous interest in developing mild ecofriendly Lewis acids for organic synthesis, we and others have been developing BiCl_3 as mild Lewis acid in organic synthesis²⁷. This has emerged as promising ecofriendly non toxic Lewis acid catalyst including Knoevenagel reactions²⁸. Our own interest²⁷ and successful applications of bismuth trichloride as mild Lewis acid promoter prompted us to further explore its use in the production of 1,4-dihydropyridines, which forms the basic thrust of the present communication. When BiCl_3 , aldehyde, 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds and ammonium acetate are heated at 60 °C under solvent free condition DHPs are obtained in excellent yields (Scheme 1).

The investigation of present work was initiated with 2 mol% BiCl_3 , *para*-formaldehyde, ethylacetoacetate and ammonium acetate (1 : 2 : 2) by thoroughly mixing/stirring the contents at 60 °C temperature under solvent free conditions but isolated yield was 75%. Like this, we used varying quantities of catalyst, viz. from 2 mol% to 10 mol% and optimized the catalyst quantity i.e. 10 mol% and get excellent results. Using less amount of catalyst resulted in the decrease of product yield while increasing

the amount of catalyst did not show any significant effect on the reaction rate as well as yields. To check the efficacy and applicability of this catalyst we could successfully obtain a range of desired products in 85–95% yields (Table 1) and reaction completes within 12–20 min.

Conclusions :

In conclusion, the present protocol employing BiCl_3 is mild, efficient and environment benign protocol for the synthesis of Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines. Products are obtained in excellent yields in very short reaction time. A simple operation procedure and solvent free condition are the attractive features of this protocol. No hazardous and unsafe by products are observed during the workup are the leading lights of this process.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Reagent-grade chemicals were purchased from commercial source and used without further purification. IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyzer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian Gemini 300 (300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel G (Merck).

General procedure for preparation of Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines :

The mixture of aldehydes (10 mmol), a 1,3-dicarbonyl compound (20 mmol), ammonium acetate (20 mmol) and BiCl_3 (0.1 mmol) was stirred at 60 °C temperature for time given in Table 1. After completion of reaction (monitored via TLC). The reaction mixture was diluted with ethyl acetate (20 mL), organic layer was washed with saturated NaHCO_3 solution (3 × 15 mL) and then with

Scheme 1

Table 1. Synthesis of substituted 1,4-dihydropyridines using 10 mol% BiCl₃ under solvent free condition

Entry.	R ₁	R ₂	Product ^a	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b
1	H	OEt	4a	13	95
2	Me	OEt	4b	15	85
3	C ₆ H ₅	OEt	4c	19	89
4	3-(NO ₂)-C ₆ H ₄	OEt	4d	20	88
5	2-Furyl	OEt	4e	13	94
6	H	OMe	4f	12	95
7	Me	OMe	4g	20	88
8	C ₆ H ₅	OMe	4h	18	87
9	3-(NO ₂)-C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4i	15	91
10	2-Furyl	OMe	4j	13	94
11	4-(OH)-C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4k	16	90
12	2-(Cl)-C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4l	15	85
13	4-(Me)-C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4m	18	90

^aThe products were characterized by comparison of their melting points and spectral (IR, ¹H NMR) data with those of authentic samples.

^bIsolated yields after recrystallization.

brine. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentration under reduced pressure gave crude product which was purified by recrystallization from ethyl acetate-ether mixture.

Representative spectral data :

(4a) : m.p. 171–173 °C. IR (KBr) : 3352, 3107, 2987, 2898, 1693, 1654, 1507 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 1.30 (6H, t, *J* 3.48), 2.19 (2H, s), 3.26 (6H, s), 4.43 (4H, q, *J* 7.17), 8.70 (1H, s).

(4b) : m.p. 128–130 °C. IR (KBr) : 3345, 2963, 1697, 1642, 1492 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 0.96 (3H, d, *J* 6.45), 1.27 (6H, t, *J* 7.05), 2.26 (6H, s), 3.82 (1H, q, *J* 6.45), 4.12 (4H, m), 5.45 (1H, s); MS : (*m/z*) 267.14 (M⁺), 265, 252, 236, 224, 220, 208, 196, 192, 178, 164, 150, 77, 43.

(4c) : m.p. 159–160 °C. IR (KBr) : 3341, 2981, 1687, 1650, 1488 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 1.19 (6H, t), 2.33 (6H, s), 4.04 (4H, m), 4.98 (1H, s), 5.52 (1H, s), 7.11–7.28 (5H, m); MS : (*m/z*) 329.16 (M⁺), 327, 282, 254, 252, 236, 224, 210, 196, 180, 139.

(4d) : m.p. 160–162 °C. IR (KBr) : 3344, 3090, 2989, 2932, 1705, 1645; 1524, 1487 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 1.19 (6H, t), 2.36 (6H, s), 4.03 (4H, m), 5.09 (1H, s), 5.66 (1H, s), 7.34 (1H, m), 7.62 (1H, m), 7.98 (1H, m), 8.11 (1H, m); MS : (*m/z*) 374.14 (M⁺), 355, 327, 299, 281, 252, 224, 196, 150, 127, 77, 43.

(4e) : m.p. 165–168 °C. IR (KBr) : 3345, 2982, 1699, 1650, 1488 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 1.23 (6H, t, *J* 7.11), 2.33 (6H, s), 4.07 (4H, m), 5.19 (1H, s), 5.69

(1H, s), 5.94 (1H, d, *J* 3.18), 6.20 (1H, dd, *J* 1.86, 1.86), 7.21 (1H, d, *J* 1.62); MS : (*m/z*) 319.14 (M⁺), 317, 290, 262, 246, 245, 218, 214, 174, 144, 115.

(4f) : m.p. 209–211 °C. IR (KBr) : 3345, 3107, 3005, 2949, 1697, 1646, 1505, 1431, 1383 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 2.85 (6H, s), 3.72 (2H, s), 3.93 (6H, s), 8.70 (1H, s); MS : (*m/z*) 225.10 (M⁺), 224, 223, 210, 192, 165, 164, 132, 120, 104, 77, 43.

(4g) : m.p. 154–155 °C. IR (KBr) : 3341, 3266, 3108, 2949, 1680, 1649 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 0.94 (3H, d, *J* 6.30), 2.27 (6H, s), 3.71 (6H, s), 3.77 (1H, q, *J* 6.5), 5.52 (1H, s); MS : (*m/z*) 239.11 (M⁺), 224, 208, 192, 178, 164, 149, 120, 43.

(4h) : m.p. 194–196 °C. IR (KBr) : 3343, 3081, 3026, 2950, 1699, 1649 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 2.34 (6H, s), 3.64 (6H, s), 5.00 (1H, s), 5.58 (1H, s), 7.12–7.25 (5H, m); MS : (*m/z*) 301.13 (M⁺), 299, 267, 236, 224, 210, 192, 164, 77.

(4i) : m.p. 211–212 °C. IR (KBr) : 3349, 3005, 2953, 1704, 1650, 1528 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 2.37 (6H, s), 3.64 (6H, s), 5.10 (1H, s), 5.71 (1H, s), 7.25 (1H, t, *J* 7.89), 7.61 (1H, m), 7.98 (1H, m), 8.08 (1H, t, *J* 1.84); MS : (*m/z*) 346.11 (M⁺), 344, 328, 327, 313, 297, 281, 224, 192, 152, 115, 43.

(4j) : m.p. 193–194 °C. IR (KBr) : 3344, 2951, 1698, 1651, 1492, 1434 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 2.34 (6H, s), 3.70 (6H, s), 5.19 (1H, s), 5.70 (1H, s), 5.92 (1H, d, *J* 3.21), 6.20 (1H, dd, *J* 1.90, 1.70), 7.21 (1H, d, *J* 1.66).

(4k) : m.p. 230–232 °C. IR (KBr) : 3329, 3001, 2953, 1681, 1650, 1611, 1589 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 2.33 (6H, s), 3.64 (6H, s), 4.70 (1H, s), 4.92 (1H, s), 5.57 (1H, s), 6.65 (2H, d, *J* 6.60), 7.10 (2H, d, *J* 6.66).

(4m) : m.p. 175–177 °C. IR (KBr) : 3314, 3105, 2942, 1697, 1655, 1495 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 2.27 (3H, s), 2.33 (6H, s), 3.64 (6H, s), 4.96 (1H, s), 5.62 (1H, s), 7.00 (2H, d, *J* 8.01), 7.14 (2H, d, *J* 8.07); MS : (*m/z*) 315.14 (M⁺), 313, 281, 250, 224, 192, 152, 115, 43.

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